

Non-Traditional Security Issues at Myanmar-India Border (1988-2008)

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Abstract

Before the end of the Cold War, majority of the countries mainly focused on the security of their countries by means of military forces. However, after the end of the Cold War, coupled with the rapid currents of globalization have reshaped the international environment and brought on new emphases on the notion of Non-Traditional Security (NTS) issues. At the India-Myanmar border, the concept of non-traditional security issues has been increasingly regarded as a better and comprehensive approach in dealing with the kind of security threats. Majority of the social issues at the two bordering areas are: arms smuggling; drugs trafficking; illegal migrant and refugees problem. Regarding the opium, the cultivation was closely related with insurgency movements because all insurgent groups relied on opium trade and bought arms with that money. Concerning about the illegal migrant problem, some of Myanmar in Dry Zone and Chin migrated into Mizoram due to the economic and environmental situation. The movement of refugees from Myanmar to India was caused by insurgency, political belief and the creation of conditions in the areas of conflict between Myanmar government troops and insurgents. These incidents contributed to mutual misunderstanding among Myanmar and Indian governments viewing the other side as providing shelter and support to groups opposing to the authority of their government.

Key words: Trans National Organized Crimes (TNC), Socio-economic Problems, Indo-Myanmar Border

Scope and Objective of the Study

To analyze and contend the field, this paper will explore the causes for the occurrence of NTS issues. These issues are situated in relations to developments in Myanmar and proximate inter-state interaction. The objective of this paper will mainly focus on the implications of these issues in the broader context of regional cooperation.

Research Methodology

The research methods used in this paper are comparative research, survey research and interview methods. Comparative method is used to examine how the two governments solved these problems in different ways. Interviews are also made to assess the finding qualitative term.

Hypothesis

Focusing on this objective, the following questions will be answered in this paper: Why did the NTS issues occur? What lessons can be learnt from this analysis? What is the future prospect?

Traditionally, security of a country had been enunciated in terms of national boundaries, external threats and internal disorder. Before the end of the Cold War, the main reasons for conflicts and wars varied from establishing sovereignty, acquiring territories spreading religion, ideologies, imposing political systems, acquiring mineral wealth and resources. At that time, human security was ignored by majority of the countries. The end of the Cold War, coupled with the rapid currents of globalization have reshaped the international environment and brought on new emphases on the notion of Non-Traditional Security (NTS) issues. It has also highlighted global problems beyond the capacity of any single state to solve. These include terrorism, arms smuggling, drug trafficking, human trafficking, illegal migrant problem, refugee problem, outbreak of diseases, environmental problem, poverty, piracy, money laundry and food insecurity. At the Myanmar-India border region, the non-traditional security issues emerge to challenge the conventional domain security continuing to both

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countries security and military threats. Majority of the social issues at the two bordering area are: arms smuggling; drugs trafficking; illegal migrant and refugees problem.

Arms Smuggling

Most of the arms smuggling took place along the two bordering areas and majority of the traffickers were insurgent groups of both countries. The constant movement of people in areas around the two borders was a major factor for the influx of arms. In many cases, the ethnic groups lived on both sides of the border and this made the smuggling in arms. The smuggled weapons mostly came from Portugal, Russia and Bulgaria and the major suppliers of the arms were the Asian countries.

According to Figure 1, the major suppliers of small arms into the India-Myanmar bordering area were from China, they took a transit at Vietnam, Cambodia, Thailand and Singapore. From those transits, small arms came into Myanmar and the second transit point was insurgents' strongholds. These small arms came into the two bordering areas through the black markets. Besides, through the South Asian militants: Jammu and Kashmir outfits; Punjab extremists; Nepalese Maoist and Myanmar insurgent groups, the small arms were smuggling into Indo-Myanmar border.

Source: South Asia's Fractured: Arms Conflict, Narcotic and Small Arms Proliferation in Northeast India, p.25

Source: <http://www.idsa-india.org/nfeb.5.html>

Figure 1. Vital weapon trafficking routes and sources into India-Myanmar border

Figure 2. Cox's Bazaar vital weapon trafficking route into India-Myanmar border

The militants in the Northeast India and Northwest Myanmar aided by the Inter-Services Intelligence (ISI) of Pakistan got their arms supply from the flourishing arms market in the Far East. The main transit port in the region was the harbour city of Cox's Bazaar. According to Figure (2) the arms trade of Cox's Bazaar had also been noticed in the coastal areas, including Chittagong post. Two islets of the Indian Island: Landsfall Island; Martin's Island (between the Coco Island and North Andaman island) were the other major transit points to the Ocean. Thus, Indian Ocean was a strategic passage for all kinds of trafficking, particularly weapons, but also precious stones, woods and all sorts of drugs. In addition to Cox's Bazaar, Tamu Bazaar at the Myanmar-Manipur border was a Bazaar where the insurgent groups brought the small arms.

The impact of small arms showed that women and children had been the worst sufferers at the two bordering areas. In that region, there had increased number of women and children who had been seriously affected by the massive influx of arms and the state of insurgency. Women had been the targets of sustained and frequently brutal violence committed by both Myanmar and India insurgent groups.

The extensive proliferation of arms combined with narcotics is providing to be the most disabling factor in the security of the both countries and their societies. The arm- drugs unit fulfills two different requirements: one is that of the drug traffickers to have large quantities of weapons to arm the forces which ensure the control and defence of vast plantation areas of refining laboratories; the other requirement is that of arms trafficker who uses arms in exchange for purchasing large quantities of drugs without any other costly go-between.

To become the weapons free zone, it is necessary to give emphasis on effective tackling programme on the massive influx of weapons. It is not enough only by anti-arms trafficking operations. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt an ideal disarmament programme that should incorporate: stress peace with honour and not surrender; ideally concentrate in bringing in the entire group; militants to be publicly treated with decency and respect; involve the militants who have surrendered in working for the development of areas in which they have operated; involve NGOs with requisite experience.

Drug Trafficking

Drug trafficking was another source of considerable income for the insurrection of that region and most of the ethnic and political insurrections in Northeast India and Northwest Myanmar involved in the drug trafficking network. India was a producer of caffeine and ephedrine (the bases used for amphetamine) and those products were easily exported to Myanmar. In the opposite direction, the processed drugs were routed to Calcutta and Cox's Bazaar.

Source: South Asia's Fractured: Arms Conflict, Narcotic and Small Arms Proliferation in Northeast India, p.167

Figure 3. Major drug routes and sources in and around South and Southeast Asia

According to Figure 3, the majority of the drugs came from Myanmar which was major transit of the Golden Triangle (Myanmar, Thailand and Laos), Thailand via Myanmar and Afghanistan and Pakistan via India into Indo- Myanmar border. Manipur, Mizoram and Nagaland were the floodgates for smuggling of at least twenty kg of heroin every day. Heroin was sold under different brands such as “two lions and globe”, “double globe”, “five stars” and “dangerous”. From poppy fields in Northeast Myanmar, opium as well as heroin was transported by road, through Bhamaw, Lashio and Mandalay to Northeast India. There were main drug trafficking routes leading from Western Myanmar to the Indian states of Nagaland, Manipur and Mizoram. The foremost route began in Mandalay, continuing through Myonywar and Kalewa, where it split to the Tamu-Moreh border crossing and the Indian Road 39, in Manipur and southward, to Hri-Champhai, into Mizoram.

Some inhabitants of the hilly terrain of Indo- Myanmar border in Aizwal and Chhim Tuipui districts had cultivated opium poppy under cover of thick jungle. Mizoram was an important trading port of acetic anhydride which is required for the manufacture of heroin from India to Myanmar. The lack of security posts at border points coupled with inadequate Northeast India security staff led to heroin freely entering into the two bordering regions. There were over twenty heroin refining units along the Indo-Myanmar border during 1990s. The narcotic drugs industry at India- Myanmar border with its annual profits about US \$ 350 billion ranked as the world's most successful illegal enterprise followed closely by the arms industry.

During the short span of time, the problem of heroin addiction reached alarming situation. A social breakdown of addict reveals that largest number was from middle income categories with a high per cent of young persons in the age group thirteen to thirty five and twenty two per cent of them were unemployed. Hundreds of youths became prey to it not only in urban area but also in rural areas. Addiction to heroin had outstripped all other forms of drugs abuse and the problem had acquired dangerous proportion with the discovery of Human Immune Virus/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (HIV/AIDS) amongst intravenous drug users of the region.

Although the two governments set up an inter-ministerial Central Committee for Drug Abuse and Control to seize and combat the drug problem, drug eradication demanded not only the seizure and destruction of drugs but also a wide range of actives, including the provision of substitute crops and the construction of a road network for taking the products to market. There was a substantial reduction of the cultivation of opium at the two bordering areas. However, with methamphetamines coming into the picture of drug production and drugs trafficking, the reduction of opium cultivation was not enough. Methamphetamines were produced from precursor chemicals which were not produced in Myanmar but which were supplied to use as refineries in remote areas of Myanmar.

On the other hand, the two governments focused only on suppression of the gangs and outbreak of HIV/AIDS problems so it is necessary to give emphasis on its effect on environment. There are two points that need to be noted while analyzing the impact of drug on the environment of the region. Firstly, it has direct impact on environment through disturbing eco- system by clearing of forest areas to cultivate the crops. Secondly, the claims over the land and other natural resources finally it led to insurgency. The exact type of environmental damage depends on how and where drug producers grow plants, process them chemically and dispose of water products. There are various methods used by the cultivators to clear land in preparation for planting. The most widely used method commonly referred to as "slash and burn" agriculture, involved the felling and burning of trees which harmed the forests irreparably.

In addition, during the cultivation of coca plantations and opium poppy, cultivators used powerful herbicides pesticides and fertilizers to protect and enhance the growth of the crops. Given without any technical expertise or consideration of harmful effects on the environment, the use those chemicals in due course rendered the soil sterile. In the process of maceration and washing coca leaf, processors discarded large quantities of gasoline, kerosene, sulfuric acid, ammonia sodium carbonate and lime on the ground and into nearby water-ways. Therefore, using of unsafe and illegal methods, cocaine and heroin processors dump vast quantities of toxic chemical substances and waste byproducts of the extraction process into countless small rivers and water courses into local sewage systems.

Moreover, to build the refining units, it is necessary to get enough land and in that regard, several insurgent groups claimed that majority of Indo-Myanmar border areas were

their own. Based on that point, several fighting and criminal cases occurred among those groups at the two bordering areas and all of the victims were civilians. Among them, majority of the victims were women and children who were sexual abused. Besides, children were made to act as drug couriers especially the street children. In some communities, street children survived by producing drugs, acting as couriers, working as dealers and providing protection through surveillance for the local drug syndicate. Moreover, because of the violence torn region, the situation seriously affects on the development of the children growing up with the disruption of education.

Illegal Migrant and Other Problems

Cross border migration in India was a complex issue and its dimensions were not only economic, political and social but also administrative and cartographic. At the Indo-Myanmar border area, mostly all of the illegal migrants were Chin and some Myanmar from Mandalay and a little from Dry Zone of Myanmar. Economic motivations underpinned the great majority of Chin and Myanmar migratory movements into India. The major causes for Chin illegal migrants into India were- not because of poverty, but to get better job and to use India as a transit point to migrate into America. Among them, some of them migrated into India for occasional environmental disaster but all of them migrated into Mizoram because Mizoram was one and only peaceful state among the seven states of Northeast India and the Mizo are the same tribes of Chin.

The problem of immigration arose out of the different levels of economic development between Myanmar and India. Before 1988, Myanmar had a centrally planned economy which placed emphasis on economic self-reliance. At that time, India had a market economy and after Mizo rebellions' negotiation with the government, it became one and only peaceful and developed state. This prosperity created a demand for labour in Mizoram and Chin and some Myanmar workers took advantage to go and work.

Since most of them left Myanmar illegally, they had no recourse to legal protection and ran the risk of being prosecuted once they got back to their home. Nevertheless, Myanmar migrant workers were abused in other ways by their employers. Some Myanmar workers were forced to work long hours without getting any overtime pay. Under the registration regulation, a migrant worker conflict with his or her employer had to seek a new employer within seven days or deportation. To control the illegal migrant problems, it is necessary for both governments to give special emphasis on controlling programme. Practically, there were several weaknesses of both governments on those issues.

Besides those people, there were several refugees at Indo-Myanmar border. There were three kinds of refugees at Indo-Myanmar border: the first was genuine refugees who lived along the war zone or areas controlled by insurgents; the second was the political refugees, Myanmar students who fled Myanmar during 1988 crises; the third was the people who were the rank-and-file and family members of Chin National Front (CNF) insurgents. The majority groups at Indo-Myanmar border were political refugees. During 1988 to 1993, India promptly endeavored to support all the Myanmar democratic movements, starting with the large number of students and rebels who fled Myanmar.

Crossing the Indo-Myanmar border, Myanmar exile students refuge in the State of Mizoram, Manipur, Nagaland and Arunachal Pradesh and India allowed 800 dissident students to shelter within her states during 1990s. Refugees' camps were set up in the Northeast to welcome those refugees as India had already defined in South Block its open-door policy for Myanmar students and activists. India had set up three refugee camps in Manipur, the main camp called the Burmese Refugees Camp in Leikhun, located sixty four kilometers from the

Indo-Myanmar border in the summer of 1988. Other camps were set up by local authorities in Champhai, twenty four kilometers from Myanmar and Nagaland. There were altogether 15,000 official Myanmar refugees all over India. Those people were given Rs. 1,400 per month as a Subsistence Allowance by the UNHCR. Among the 1,500 refugees, who registered in New Delhi, only 200 to 300 were true political activists, committed to the struggle against the Myanmar government.

In order to prevent the NTS issues, it is necessary for both countries to cooperate by mean of exchanging information and operating counter trafficking. Through the illegal migration, the drug trafficking, smuggling of arms and money laundering were found. Indo-Myanmar cooperation to counter drug smuggling, narcotics crimes, illegal migration and refugee problems were acknowledged as imperatives for the foreign policies of the both countries. There was lack of cooperation between the two countries in combating TNS issues before 1992. Since 1992, with the changing of India's policy towards Myanmar, greater emphasis came to be placed by Myanmar on the need to move into practical areas of cooperation, such as the exchange of information, intelligence and expertise among the security agencies of the two countries.

It is also necessary to do several emphases on the problem of the two bordering area peoples and problem solving is necessary at all levels: historical, economic, social and political. Indeed, it needs to start Confidence Building Measures (CBM) between the governments and the various dissenting ethnic groups of the two bordering areas. In order to find long term solutions in those regions, approaches have to be taken that involve individuals as well as communities, working together for everyone benefit.

Before reaching the final conclusion, this paper would like to call upon the three questions, why did the NTS issues occur? What lessons can be learnt from this analysis? What is the future prospect? In response to the question on the causes for the occurrence of TNC, this study finds that the region had the potential for the proliferation of small arms and narcotics because of poverty stricken population, underdevelopment and nascent nationalism. In order to build a peaceful region, it is necessary to solve the illegal migrant problem. Through the illegal migration, the problem of drug trafficking, smuggling of arms and money laundering were found. Since the peace and stability of the two bordering areas could maintain the tranquility of the region, it is necessary for both governments to cooperate and effectively implement not only anti trafficking operation but also border area development programme.

References

Reports

- Myanmar Narcotic Report. (1997). CCDAC, The Government of the Union of Myanmar, Yangon
- Special Anti-Trafficking Unit's 2006 Annual Report. (2006). Myanmar Police Organization, MOH, Nay Pyi Taw
- The CIA Report in the Friday Times, September 1993
- The CIA Report in the Friday Times, September 2004

Books

- Ahmed, Imtiz, Mal. (2003). "Development, Environmental Insecurity and Militarism in South Asia", Allahabad, Macmillan
- Babu, Gikishoore. (2000). "India and Neighbors", Lancer Publication, New Delhi
- CCDAC. (2008). "Endeavour of Myanmar for Eliminations of Narcotic Drugs", CCDAC, The Government of the Union of Myanmar, Nay Pyi Taw

- Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2000). "International Migration Policies", Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Geneva
- Kartha, Tara. (1993). "Spread of Arms and Instability", India, Strategic Analysis, May 1993
- Kartha, Tara. (1999). "Non-Conventional threat to Security: Threat from the Proliferation of Light Weapons and Narcotics", India, Strategic Analysis, 1999
- Kham Aung, Pol. Col. (2004). "Suppression of Narcotic Drugs", Seminar on Understanding Myanmar, Yangon, MICT Park, 27-28 January 2004
- Kumar, Sumita. (2003). "Drugs Trafficking in the Golden Triangle", IDSA, New Delhi
- Ministry of Home Affairs. (2007). "Drug Control Endeavour in the Union of Myanmar in 2006", Ministry of Home Affairs, Yangon
- Nepam, Binalakshmi. (2006). "South Asia's Fractured: Arms Conflict, Narcotics and Small Arms Proliferation In Northeast India", Mittal Publications, New Delhi
- Oxford University Press. (2005). "Problem of Statelessness", Oxford University Press, London
- Smith, Martin, "Burma: Insurgency and Politics of Ethnicity", Zed Books, London
- Tin Mmaung Maung Than. (2007). "Mapping the Contours of Human Security Challenges in Myanmar", Utopia Press Pte Ltd, Singapore
- UNDCP. (2005). "Chemical Control in the Fight against Illicit Drug Production", UNDCP, Geneva
- UNIDIR. (2000). "Interrelationships between Illicit Trafficking in Small Arms, Drugs Trafficking and Terrorist Groups", UNIDIR, Geneva
- jynfytm;udk;ykqdef%dk;rsm;\tzsuftarSmufvkyf&yfrsm; (The Conspiracy of Treasonous Minions within the Myanmar Naing and Traitorous Cohorts Abroad), 1st printing, Yangon, the News and Periodicals Enterprise, 23 October, 1990
- &efoIYZGJYpnf;yHk? taemufajrmufwdkif;ppfXmecsKyf (The Structure of Enemy, Northwest Military Command), 1999

Newspapers

- North East Sun*, 10.12.1999
- North East Sun*, 14.5. 2003
- Shillong Times*, 6.5.1999
- Shillong Times*, 20.1. 2001
- Shillong Times*, 11.10. 2005
- The New Light of Myanmar*, 8.9.1998
- The New light of Myanmar*, 26.7. 2004
- The Statesman*, 30.10.2005

Journals

- Drug Control Programme of Myanmar*, 2 (1), Yangon, UNDCP, October 1998
- Janes Defense Weekly*, 24.5.1988
- Janes Defense Weekly*, 2.1.2002